

PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS TEACHING AND THEIR LEVEL OF ASPIRATION

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Abstract

The research paper examines "Primary School Teachers' Attitude towards teaching and their Level of Aspiration" by sampling 100 teachers from 25 schools in the Mandi district of Himachal Pradesh. Effect of three independent variables namely gender (male/ female), qualification (under graduated / graduated) and income groups (high income / low income) were studied. The study aimed to understand the correlation between teachers' attitude towards teaching and their level of aspiration. The findings indicated a positive correlation between higher levels of aspiration have a more favourable attitude towards teaching. Interestingly, there was no significant difference between male and female primary school teachers' attitudes, although male teachers displayed a slightly more favorable attitude towards teaching. The undergraduate teachers with a high income had a more favourable attitude towards teaching than the graduate Primary School teachers. As far as level of Aspiration is concerned among males and females, there are female teachers; undergraduates over graduates with high income possess high level of aspirations than teachers with same qualification and low-income group.

Key words: *Primary schools, Teachers' attitude, Attitude towards teaching and Level of Aspiration.*

Introduction: "There is a joy in life that comes as a result of labour. There is joy in knowing that you have done your best, that you have served your best, that you have given the best of your service to the task at hand."

W.R. Greshan

Teachers are essential in influencing the future because they mold young minds, convey knowledge, and encourage critical thinking. Their perspectives on education have a big impact

on the classroom climate and the academic development of the pupils. Teachers' aspirations have a big influence on how they teach, how the classroom works, and eventually, how well students do. Teachers' passion, dedication, and confidence in the transforming power of education are reflected in their attitude toward their work. A teacher's energy, outlook, and dedication foster a learning environment where students are inspired to experiment, ask questions, and achieve success. High aspiration among educators frequently translates into a desire to be creative, adjust to different learning styles, and always enhance their pedagogical approaches. Furthermore, there is an inherent connection between a teacher's aspirations and their own professional development. Teachers who are driven to grow personally are more likely to look for innovative ways to teach, use technology well, and participate in continuing education. Teachers gain from this constant quest of perfection, and it also has a favorable impact on the learning environment they offer their students. However, a variety of circumstances, including institutional support, the availability of resources, individual motivations, and the dominant educational culture, can lead to large variations in the aspiration levels among instructors. Some instructors may be prevented from realizing their full potential by obstacles in the educational system or restricted access to opportunities for professional growth, which can have an effect on their level of passion and aspiration. Gaining an understanding of the relationship between a teacher's aspirations and their teaching attitude is essential to understanding the dynamics of the educational environment. It emphasizes how important it is to create an atmosphere that supports and encourages teachers so they can continue to have a great deal of passion, commitment, and aspiration for teaching and influencing the next generation.

So, by saying the teacher “The builder of Nation” we here are not exaggerating the supreme importance. It is almost true that the quality of a citizen depends upon the education he had and education in a country in return.

Statement of the Problem: *“PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS’ ATTITUDE TOWARDS TEACHING AND THEIR LEVEL OF ASPIRATION”*

Definitions of the key Terms

Teachers’ Attitude: Attitude may be defined as a feeling or disposition in favour of against an object, idea, person, or group. In this connection one may study attitudes which may be a matter of degree of approval or disapproval.

G. W. All Port defines attitude as “A mental or neural state of readiness, organized, through experience, exerting a directive or dynamic influence upon the individuals to all objects and situations with which it is related.”

Attitude towards Teaching: Attitude towards teaching may be positive or favourable attitude, negative or unfavorable attitude.

A positive attitude towards teaching is the one in which the teacher favors or likes the task of teaching and the task is interesting and easier for him.

A negative attitude towards teaching is one which evokes the feeling of disfavor and disapproval of the teacher towards teaching, and for him the teaching work is hard and tedious.

So here in the study teachers’ attitude towards the teaching profession means liking, disliking and interest towards teaching profession.

Level of Aspiration: Level of aspiration is an important aspect of personality, which deserves consideration about academic attainment of a student.

A term coined by *Dembo* (1931), a student of Lewin, the notion of level of aspiration is invoked in reference to the goal striving behaviour of an individual presented with a task, come out of which can be measured on an achievement scale.

So here in the study level of aspiration of teachers refers to his/her level of achievement in teaching profession in future.

Primary Schools: Primary schools here stands for all the Government Primary Schools in Balh and Mandi Sadar blocks of District Mandi of H.P.

Significance of the Study: Education is perceived to be a universal phenomenon. It is adequately organized and regulated through formal institutions like schools and colleges. The quality, competence and character of a teacher are undoubtedly very significant. There is a great number of retentions at the primary stage of education in our country. To avoid the problem of retention and to achieve the target of universal primary education, it is very important to know the reason behind all their problems.

Nothing is more important than to secure a sufficient supply of high quality to the teaching, providing them with best possible professional preparation and to create in them satisfactory condition of work, to make their teaching more effecting.

There is an immediate need to know the causes of dissatisfaction among the primary school teachers if better services are expected of them. The causes that add to the dissatisfaction need to be immediately and promptly eliminated. Although different scholars in this direction have made efforts yet there is a wide scope to plug the stigma of dissatisfaction among the

primary school teachers. Therefore, the investigator tried to present humbly a venture in this direction.

Objectives of the Study

- (1) To study the relationship between primary schools teachers' attitude and their level of aspiration towards teaching.
- (2) To compare the attitude of male and female primary school teachers towards teaching.
- (3) To compare the attitude of the graduate and under graduate primary school teachers towards teaching.
- (4) To compare the attitude of the high and low income group primary school teachers towards teaching.
- (5) To compare the level of aspiration of the male and female primary school teachers.
- (6) To compare level of aspiration of the graduate and under graduate primary school teachers.
- (7) To compare the level of aspiration of the high and low-income group primary school teachers.

Hypothesis

- (1) There is no significant relationship of attitude of primary school teachers and their level of aspiration.
- (2) There is no significant difference between attitude of male and female primary school teachers towards teaching.
- (3) There is no significant difference in attitude of undergraduate and graduate primary school teachers towards teaching.
- (4) There is no significant difference in attitude of high- Income and low-Income group primary school teachers towards teaching.
- (5) There is no significant difference in level of aspiration of male and female primary school teachers.
- (6) There is no significant difference in the level of aspiration of undergraduate and graduate primary school teachers.
- (7) There is no significant difference in the level of aspiration of high- and low-income group of primary school teachers.

Delimitation of the Study: When the problem is delimited to be specified on exact aspects, the researcher on sure grounds gets fully acquainted with the scope of the problem. Keeping in view the limited resources, limited finances,

time capacity and energies, the investigators have delimited the present problem as follows:

1. The study was confined to the government primary schools in district Mandi of Himachal Pradesh.
2. Teachers teaching in government primary schools comprise the sample.
3. Only teacher's attitude towards teaching and their level of aspiration as dependent variable were taken for study.
4. The study is restricted to three independent variables i.e. Gender, qualification and income groups.

Sr. No.	Name of school	Gender		Qualification		Income	
		Male	Female	Under Graduate	Graduate	Low Income	High Income
1	Govt. Pry. School Bagla	2	3	3	2	1	4
2	Govt. Pry. School Garsol	2	1	2	1	-	3
3	Govt. Pry. School Chandyal	3	2	3	2	4	1
4	Govt. Pry. School Gaggal	-	5	3	2	2	3
5	Govt. Pry. School Chattru	2	2	1	3	3	1
6	Govt. Central Pry. School Kummi	5	2	3	4	6	1
7	GPS Rajgarh	1	3	2	2	-	4
8	GPS Rigad	2	1	2	1	1	2
9	GPS Baggi	1	5	4	2	2	4
10	GPS Bhour	2	2	2	2	3	1
11	GPS Kanaid	1	2	-	3	1	2
12	GPS Gutkar	1	2	2	1	2	1
13	GPS Balh Mandi	1	1	-	2	-	2
14	GPS Purani Mandi	1	1	-	2	-	2
15	Govt. Central Pry. School Nalsar	1	4	5	-	2	3

Research Methodology: The purpose of present study is to investigate teachers' attitude towards teaching and their level of aspiration. For this purpose, the "Survey" method was used. Two questionnaires, one for collecting information about attitude of teachers towards teaching and the others for knowing their level of aspiration, were used.

(a) Population and Sample: Out of 20 blocks of District Mandi, two blocks namely Balh , Mandi Sadar and 25 Primary Schools from same blocks were selected randomly. All the teachers working in these schools were included in the sample on the basis of willingness of the teachers to provide requisite information.

In the Present study sample was comprised of 100 Primary School Teachers working in the 25 Primary Schools of Balh and Sadar Mandi blocks in District Mandi of Himachal Pradesh.

Table-1

Sr. No.	Name of school	Gender		Qualification		Income	
		Male	Female	Under Graduate	Graduate	Low Income	High Income
16	GPS Lohara	1	3	3	1	3	1
17	GPS Paddal Mandi	2	4	1	5	4	2
18	GPS Diargi	3	2	2	3	1	4
19	GPS U-Block Mandi	-	3	3	-	1	2
20	Govt. Middle School Dhaban	1	3	2	2	-	4
21	GPS Dadour	2	2	2	2	-	4
22	GPS Bhangrotu	-	3	3	-	1	2
23	GPS Ratti	-	2	2	-	-	2
24	GPS Tawan	2	3	5	-	4	1
25	GPS Kot	1	2	3	-	3	-

(b) Tools Used: The following two Questionnaires were used in the present study:

(I) Teachers' Attitude Inventory: Teachers' attitude inventory consisted of 46-items constructed and standardized by Sujata Mishra, Research Scholar of Department of Education, Kurukshetra University for her doctoral thesis in the year 1999.

1) Status of Teaching 2) Teaching Skill 3) Pupils Achievement 4) Social Climate 5) Teachers' Expectation

(II) Level of Aspiration Inventory: Level of aspiration is an important aspect of personality. It creates so many vital problems among the teachers. The present level of aspiration inventory developed by Sujata Mishra was used to measure level of aspiration of primary school teachers. The inventory measures the following aspects:

1) Parental and Personal Wishes. 2) Social Expectation. 3) Desire for perfection. 4) Economic and cultural background. 5) Professional attitude. 6) Values and interest.

(c) Procedure of Data Collection: Questionnaires were given to the selected sample of teachers. Before giving the questionnaire proper rapport was established with the subjects. Then the purpose of the Questionnaires was explained to them and they were assured that their responses would be kept confidential, so they were requested to be free, frank, honest and sincere in answering the questions.

(d) Scoring of the Scale and Inventory: The attitude Inventory and level of aspiration questionnaire consists of 46 items and 44 items respectively. The answers for all the questions were collected at-five-point scale. The five points were:

1) Strongly agree 2) Agree 3) Unclaimed 4) Disagree 5) Strongly Disagree.

In positive statements those who put tick (✓) mark against strongly agree were awarded 5 marks, agree was given 4 marks, undecided 3 marks, disagree 2 marks and strongly disagree 1 mark respectively. There was no negative item.

Table-2: Relationship between Teachers Attitude and their Level of Aspiration towards Teaching.

Variables	N	df	Co-efficient of Correlation
Teachers' Attitude towards teaching.	100	98	0.4176**
Level of aspiration	100		

*Note: ** indicates significant at 0.01 level of significance.*

Value of significance at 0.01 level with df =98 is .257. From the above table-2, it can be clearly

observed that the coefficient of co-relation is 0.4176 which is higher than the table value. It means that the teachers' attitude towards teaching and their level of aspiration are positively correlated with each other. It shows that teachers with a higher level of aspiration had more favorable attitude towards teaching. The correlation was very high between teachers' attitude towards teaching and their level of aspiration.

Table-3: Differences in Attitude of Male and Female Primary School Teachers towards Teaching

Group of Teachers	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio
Male	170.11	11.72	0.73 NS
Female	168.87	12.64	

Note: NS indicates not significant at any level of significance.

The table value of 't' for degree of freedom at 0.01 level of significance =2.63 The table value of 't' for degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance =1.985 It can be observed from the table-3 that mean scores for attitude of male and female primary school teachers towards teaching are 170.11 and 168.87 with S.D. of 11.72 and 12.64. The t-ratio among male and female teachers came out to be 0.73. Since the calculated value is less than the table value at .05 level.

The difference in the mean scores is not significant. Hence the hypothesis is accepted. In other words, it can be said that the Primary School Teacher with respect to their sex showed no difference in their attitude towards teaching.

Table-4: Differences in Attitude of Undergraduate and Graduate Primary School Teachers towards Teaching

Group of Teachers	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio
Undergraduate	186.10	13.74	0.615 NS
Graduate	184.17	16.71	

Note: NS indicates not significant at any level of significance.

It can be observed from the table-4 that Mean scores for undergraduate teachers on the attitude scale are 186.10 and 184.17 with S.D. of 13.74 and 16.71. The t-ratio came out to be 0.615, which is not significant at any level of significance. The mean scores show the results in favour of undergraduate teachers. It indicates that the undergraduate teachers had a more favourable attitude towards teaching than the graduate Primary School teachers. Thus, the hypothesis is accepted. This may be due to higher expectations of more qualified teachers.

Table-5: Differences in Attitude of High-Income Group and Low-Income Group Primary School Teachers towards Teaching

Group of Teachers	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio
High Income	169.28	11.71	
Low Income	168.56	13.89	0.274 NS

Note: NS indicates not significant at any level of significance.

It can be observed from the table that the mean scores for High-Income group and Low-income group teachers are 169.28 and 168.56 with S.D. of 11.71 and 13.89 respectively. The t-ratio among the high-income group and low-income group Primary School teachers came out to be 0.274, which is not significant at any level significance. Thus, the hypothesis is accepted.

The difference in mean scores comes in favor of high-income group teachers. Thus, high-income group teachers had a higher positive attitude towards teaching than low-income group Primary School teachers. This result of table-5 is in accordance with the study conducted by KUNDU (1961) which indicated that high paid teachers had a more favorable attitude towards teaching than the low paid teachers.

Table-6: Differences in Level of Aspiration of Female and Male Primary School Teachers

Group of teachers	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio
Female	185.56	15.40	
Male	185.10	13.37	0.152 NS

Note: NS indicates not significant at any level of significance.

It can be observed from the table-6 that mean scores of female and male teachers are 185.56 and 185.10 with S.D. of 15.40 and 13.37 respectively. The t-ratio for male and female teachers comes out to be 0.152 which is not significant at any level of significance. Thus, the hypothesis is accepted.

Table-7: Differences in Level of Aspiration of Undergraduate and Graduate Primary School Teachers.

Group of Teachers	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio
Undergraduate	186.10	13.74	
Graduate	184.16	16.71	0.615 NS

Note: NS indicates not significant at any level of significance.

From table-7 it can be observed that the mean scores for the undergraduate and graduate are 186.10 and 184.16 with S.D. of 13.74 and 16.71 respectively. The t-ratio comes out to be 0.615. The t-ratio is less than the table value at .05 level of significance. Thus, the hypothesis is accepted. The difference in the mean scores is not significant thus it can be said that academic qualifications of the teachers had no influence on level of aspiration. Primary School Teachers irrespective of their academic qualifications had the same level of aspiration.

Table-8: Differences in Level of Aspiration of High-Income and Low-Income Group

Primary School Teachers			
Group of teachers	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio
High income group	185.73	14.27	0.157 NS
Low-income group	185.25	15.96	

Note: NS indicates not significant at any level of significance.

It can be observed from table-8 that the mean scores for the High-income group and low-income group Primary School teachers comes out to be 185.73 and 185.25 with S.D. of 14.27 and 15.96 respectively. The t-ratio comes out to be 0.157, which is not significant at any level of significance. Thus, the hypothesis is accepted.

Findings and Conclusion: The study was conducted in two parts one part was teachers' attitude towards teaching and the other was their level of aspiration. Teachers' attitude towards teaching and their level of aspiration was positively correlated. The teachers with a higher level of aspiration had a more favourable attitude towards teaching. Male and Female Primary School teachers had no significant difference, but male have slightly more favourable attitude towards teaching than their counterparts. Undergraduate Primary School teachers had a more favourable attitude towards teaching than the graduate Primary School teachers as indicated by mean values respectively. High-income group primary school teachers and low-income group teachers has no significant difference in attitude towards teaching, but mean value of High-income group is higher than low income group teachers which shows favourable attitude of high income group than low income group teachers.

Male and Female primary school teachers shows no significant difference in their levels of aspiration, but the mean values are slightly different. Undergraduate and graduate primary school teachers had the same level of aspiration, but the mean values of aspiration of Undergraduate teachers is higher than the Graduates teachers which indicate that the

Undergraduate teachers have higher Level of Aspiration in comparison to graduates. High-income and low-income group primary school teachers have almost the same level of Aspiration.

From the analysis and interpretation of data following conclusions have been drawn:

- (1) Teachers' attitude and their level of aspiration towards teaching are significantly correlated which shows that teachers with higher aspirations have a more favourable attitude towards teaching.
- (2) Male teachers had more favourable attitude towards teaching than female teachers. It may be due to the reason that female teachers are more engaged in domestic work; they have multifarious duties at home as compared to male teachers.
- (3) Undergraduate teachers have a more positive attitude than graduate teachers. It may be because of the reason that graduates' teachers. It may be because of the reason that the graduate teachers have more opportunities for their professional growth.
- (4) Female teachers have higher level of aspiration than male teachers because they feel more comfortable to deal with small children that provide the same environment as of the home environment.
- (5) Undergraduate teachers have a higher level of aspiration as compared to their counterparts because of the reason that they are satisfied with their jobs according to their qualification.
- (6) High-Income group teachers have high level of aspiration because they are more experienced, and they have more clarity and mastery of the subjects which develop interest of the teachers in the subjects.

Reference

- Adegoke, K.A. (1998).** *"The Challenges of Quality Public Education in the 21st Century"*, with Particular Reference to Nigeria: World Teachers' Day Document by Nigeria Union of Teachers 1998, P. 22.
- Bedel, Ferda. (2008).** "A Study of Interaction Among Attitudes and Personality Constructs in Early Childhood Pre-service Teachers." *Journal of Theory and Practice in Education*, ISSN: 1304-9496.
- Duatepe, Asuman, Akksu, Oylum .(2004).** *"A Study of the Attitude Towards Teaching Professions of In-Service and Pre-Service Primary School Teachers."* Pedagogy Studies Central and Eastern European Online Library (pp. 61-65).
- F.O. Fokoya. (2009).** *"A Study of Teaching Profession and Factors Inhibiting Teaching Profession in Nigeria"*. University of Ibadan.

- Good, C.V. (1959).** *“Dictionary of Education 2nd Edition.”* New York: Mc Graw Hill.
- Goodson, I. (2003).** *“Professional Knowledge, Professional Lives: Studies in Education-Maidenhead”* Open University Press.
- Hayon, L.K. (1989).** *“The International Encyclopedia of Teacher Education.”* Paragon Press: London UK (P. 83).
- Koul, L. (1985).** *“Methodology of Education Research.”* New Delhi :Vikas Publishing house Pvt. Ltd.
- Reddy, A. Venkata Rami and Babu, V. Rama Moham ,(1994).** *“Attitude of the Residential and Non-Residential School Teachers Towards Teaching.”* Perspectives in education, Volume 10(3) (pp. 155-162).
- Singh, Gurmit. (2007).** *“Job Satisfaction of Teacher of Educators in Relation their Attitude Towards Teaching.”* *Journal of all India association of educational research*, vol. 19, No. 3 & 4, September-December 2007, PP. 34-37.
- Zhihuli Fang, Asheey Carmen. (2004).** *“Pre-Service Teachers Interpretation of a Field Based Reading Block”* *Journal of Teacher Education*, Vol. 55, No. 1, January/February (pp. 39-54).
- Mechale, D. (1987).** *The International Encyclopedia of Teaching and Teacher Education.* New York: Oxford Pergamon Press.
- Memon, T.K.N.and Kaut, G.N. (1964).** *Experiments in Teacher Training*, New Delhi: Ministry of Education, Government of India.